

CONDENSATION OF ALDEHYDES WITH MALONIC ACID. PART XVIII. CONDENSATION OF 5-NITRO-2-HYDROXYBENZALDEHYDE

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5-Nitro-2-hydroxybenzaldehyde (5-nitrosalicylaldehyde) is condensed with malonic acid. It does not enter into condensation in the absence of any condensing reagent or even in the presence of glacial acetic acid. In the presence of pyridine, piperidine or a mixture of the two, it gives 5-nitro-2-hydroxybenzylidene-malonic (5-nitrosalicylidene-malonic) acid, the highest yield, so far obtained, being 84% in five hours' heating at 80°: as salicylaldehyde has always given much lower yields, the increase could be due only to the influence of the nitro group in 5 position. The corresponding mono-acid has, however, not been obtained yet from either the aldehyde or the dibasic acid.

The influence of several dissimilar groups (situated on the aromatic ring of the aldehyde) on the aldehyde-malonic acid condensation has already formed the subject of some of the papers in this series. For example, the condensation of malonic acid with vanillin (Pandya and Sodhi, *Proc. Ind. Acad. Sci.*, 1939, 9A, 512), where one hydroxy group and one methoxy group occur on the ring; with 5-bromosalicylaldehyde and with 3:5-dibromosalicylaldehyde (Pandya and Miss Pandya, *ibid.*, 1943, 12A, 164) where a hydroxy group in the *ortho* position occurs with one or two bromo groups; and some more unpublished work in theses (such as by Gauri Shankar Gupta on condensation of 3:5-dibromo-*p*-hydroxybenzaldehyde; Miss R. Pandya, on that of bromo- and nitropiperonal; and Raghunath Singh, on those of several halogenated hydroxybenzaldehydes).

The present paper deals with a nitro group and an *ortho*-hydroxy group in 5-nitro-2-hydroxybenzaldehyde (5-nitrosalicylaldehyde). The nitro group could take up, directly or indirectly, any of the four positions- 3, 4, 5 or 6. In position 5, the group

is sufficiently far from both the hydroxy and the aldehyde group and will not introduce any complication due to a hydrogen bond or chelation. The condensation in actual practice goes well and is characterised by several peculiarities.

Firstly, it offers a contrast to benzaldehyde and salicylaldehyde in not entering, under ordinary conditions, into condensation with malonic acid in the absence of any condensing base, or even in the presence of glacial acetic acid alone.

Secondly, in the presence of pyridine, piperidine or a mixture of the two, it gives 5-nitrosalicylidene-malonic acid, a dibasic acid, the analogue of which has so far not been obtained (though 5-bromo- and 3:5-dibromosalicylaldehydes gave similar products, Pandya and Miss Pandya, *loc. cit.*) from salicylaldehyde, and the analogous compound

* A part of the M.Sc. thesis of D.T. (1941) and a part of the M.Sc. thesis of O.S.S (1944), both having worked independently.

from benzaldehyde is obtained by heating with glacial acetic acid (Stuart's method) or heating without any condensing agent (Pandya and Miss Pandya, *loc. cit.*).

Thirdly, and this seems remarkable, the expected monobasic acid, 5-nitro-2-hydroxycinnamic acid, has not been obtained by any of the methods so far tried. It has not been obtained in a pure condition from the dibasic acid even. Nor was the nitrocoumarin-carboxylic acid obtained.

In the case of salicylaldehyde, the usual product has been coumarin carboxylic acid which would be formed only from salicylidene-malonic acid (Kurien and Pandya, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1934, 11, 324), which has not yet been isolated. Another product has also been isolated now (Ph. D. thesis by Raghunath Singh, unpublished), which is also quite different. It appears, however, that the presence of the nitro group in position 5 imparts a great stability to this product besides giving an increased yield.

Its identification rests on the equivalent and molecular weight determinations and on the nitrogen content; all of which agree with this structure and rule out other alternatives, which may be as under:—

Three more possibilities are suggested from recent work in this laboratory on salicylaldehyde and its chloro derivatives (unpublished, Raghunath Singh). These are:

Thus there are eight structures that are most likely; a few more could be worked out from the tetracarboxylic acid (VI) by anhydride formation, which, however, may be omitted as being less likely.

1. The product obtained gives a definite melting point which is much lower than that of (III) (which melts at 245°), and definitely higher than that of (V) which melts at 185° . So the actual melting point rules out (III) and (V).

2. The product obtained is a distinct acid, and so the nitrocoumarin (V) is again out of question.

3. The product always melts with effervescence, suggesting a dibasic acid of the malonic type. All monobasic acids are thus ruled out, namely (III), (IV) and (IX).

4. The acid gives clear indications of unsaturation: so those structures having no double bond are not indicated, such as (VI), (VII), (VIII) and (IX).

5. The ferric chloride reaction of the phenolic group suggests that a free hydroxy group is present and that there is no coumarin ring, as is involved in presence of (IV), (V), (VIII) and (IX).

6. The equivalent weight found is roughly 129: so all monobasic acids, (III), (IV) and (IX) are again excluded. In fact only (II) and (VI) are left so far. (VI) is a tetracarboxylic acid, which would probably be highly unstable, with a high melting point, and with about 89 as the equivalent weight. (II) on the other hand requires 126.5, and the experimental value is nearest to it. The molecular weight by Rast's method is also agreeable to (II) only, being 255.3; (II) requires 253.

7. Lastly, the nitrogen content agrees very well: (II) requires 5.53% (found 5.50%).

A word is necessary about the yield, which is greater in the ordinary conditions than that obtained from salicylaldehyde. For though the maximum yield of coumarin-carboxylic acid from salicylaldehyde is given as 51% (Kurien and Pandya, *loc.cit.*) and rises even to 77% with the use of special bases (Khan, Kurien and Pandya, *Proc. Ind. Acad. Sci.*, 1935, 1, 443), a recent revision of the condensation employing a pyridine-trace under the ordinary conditions gave only 30% of coumarin-carboxylic acid and 13% of another acid (Raghunath Singh, 1946, unpublished work). In the present case of 5-nitrosalicylaldehyde, the best yields came up to about 80 to 84% as can be seen from the table at the end. It can be thus seen that the nitro group in position

5, has not only given a peculiar stability to a rare condensation product, but has also increased the yield.

EXPERIMENTAL

Preparation of 5-(& 3)-Nitrosalicylaldehydes.—Salicylaldehyde was nitrated according to Miller (*Ber.*, 1887, 20, 1928) by means of fuming nitric acid at 10°. The orange precipitate that was obtained on adding this mixture to cold water contained both 5-nitro- and 3-nitro-salicylaldehyde. 5-Nitrosalicylaldehyde (m. p. 126°) came out in pale white crystals in 24% yield and the 3-nitrosalicylaldehyde (m. p. 107°) came out in 65% yield. (Mazzara gives the m.p. as 123-25° and 105-107° respectively, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1877, 1, 597). The total yield was thus 89% when separated; the total yield before separation was 98-100% of theory. The method of separation was the same as given by Miller (*loc. cit.*). The preparation was repeated several times, under identical conditions, but relative yields generally varied. Attempts to prepare each one of the nitro derivatives separately in a pure condition did not meet with success.

Condensation of 5-Nitrosalicylaldehyde

Perkin's method did not give any condensation product, as claimed by Tage (*Ber.*, 1887, 20, 2109). The dirty yellow product obtained, on the usual treatment, gave back the 5-nitrosalicylaldehyde, which was identified by means of a mixed m.p. with an authentic specimen of the aldehyde, prepared in the laboratory.

Condensation with Malonic acid but without any reagent.—The mixture of the 5-nitrosalicylaldehyde (1.7 g.) and malonic acid (1 g.) was heated first on the water-bath and as it did not fuse even after an hour's heating, it was heated on an oil-bath at 105° to 125° for 4 hours, or 12 hours heating up to 140°. No fusion took place and most of the aldehyde was recovered unchanged.

Condensation by Stuart's method with Glacial Acetic acid as a condensing agent.—When heated for 6 hours the original aldehyde was recovered (about 87%).

Condensation with Malonic acid with a Trace of Pyridine.—(i) The mixture was heated in the usual way (1:1:0.2 mol.) at 100-105° for 4 hours. The reaction started immediately, gas began to come out and a part of the aldehyde sublimed in the neck of the flask. The mass fused, but resolidified in about 45 minutes. Some aldehyde was recovered unchanged, but a pale yellow solid acid product also came out (separated by NaHCO₃ soln.). The latter was washed with chloroform, and it melted at 195-98°. Recrystallised from a mixture of benzene and alcohol, it melted at 199-201° with effervescence. 3.4 G. of 5-nitrosalicylaldehyde gave 2.5 g. of the acid, and so the yield of the dibasic acid was 49.4%. But as 0.8 g. of the aldehyde was recovered unchanged, the yield was really 61.6% of the total aldehyde used.

(ii) The condensation was repeated at lower temperatures, in order to avoid or reduce the sublimation of the aldehyde. The yield then increased. Thus condensation at 95-98° gave 2.8 g. (55.3%) yield, with 0.7 g. of unused aldehyde; so on the

aldehyde used, the yield was 69.1%. At 90° the yield was 3.1 g. or 61.2%; 0.4 g. of the aldehyde was recovered, therefore on the aldehyde used, the yield was about 80%. At 80°, five hours' heating gave 69.1% yield; deducting 0.3 g. aldehyde recovered, the yield became 84% of theory.

Condensation with more Pyridine.—The aldehyde, malonic acid and pyridine were taken in the proportion of 1:1:1 mol. Less pyridine was taken at the start, but the remainder was added to bring down the sublimed crystals of nitrosalicylaldehyde from the neck of the flask. The heating was for 6 hours on the water-bath. The yield was only 41.5%, or deducting the 20% of the aldehyde recovered, it was 49%. With two and three molecules of pyridine and 12 hours' heating on the water-bath, the yields again came up to 67.3% and 69.1% of theory.

Condensation with Piperidine as a condensing agent.—With a molecule of piperidine in place of pyridine, and heating for 6 hours on a water-bath, the yield was again low, 43%.

Condensation by Vorsatz's method with pyridine at room temperature.—The three ingredients were taken in the proportion of 1:1:10 mols. and kept at room temperature for 3 weeks. The yield was only 17%; still longer time might possibly have raised the yield.

Condensation by Robinson's method with pyridine-piperidine mixture gave an yield of 68.7%.

Condensation in presence of ether without a catalyst.—Sufficient ether was taken to make the reactants dissolved. The mixture was kept for 3 weeks; the aldehyde was recovered unchanged. Another flask of the above was kept for 3 months, but no condensation took place.

The product obtained in all the above condensations was identical. It had a bright yellow colour and melted after recrystallisation at 193° with effervescence, suggesting a dibasic acid of the malonic type. It was readily soluble in dilute alcohol, glacial acetic acid, acetone and carbon tetrachloride; sparingly soluble in benzene and ethyl acetate and insoluble in ether and chloroform. It also dissolved in strong sulphuric acid with a red colour. Its alcoholic solution gave with aqueous or alcoholic ferric chloride a deep red colour. It decolorised Baeyer's reagent in the cold. Its solution in glacial acetic acid, even the solid acid alone, decolorised readily bromine water or bromine in acetic acid. [Found: N, 5.76, 5.47, 5.50. $C_{10}H_8O_2N$ (nitrosalicylidene-malonic acid) requires N, 5.53 per cent].

Equivalent weight determination by titration against standard alkali was found to be impossible as the acid gave an orange or yellow-coloured solution with alkali, making phenolphthalein useless. A rough approximation was 110-120. As the acid gave a yellow silver salt, an average of three estimations gave the equivalent weight as 129 which is slightly higher than the expected value of 126.5.

Molecular weight determinations by Rast's method gave 260 and 255.3; $C_{10}H_8O_2N$ requires 253.0.

Several different experiments which were made to obtain a monobasic acid from this dibasic acid by different methods failed to give any clear product.

TABLE I

Mol. proportions. Aldehyde	Acid. Catalyst.		Temp.	Heated for.	Yield%	
					taken.	consume
1	+ AcONa+Ac ₂ O	(Perkin)	170-180°	8 hr.	0.0	0.0
1 : 1 : 1		glacial AcOH (Stuart)	120°	6	0.0	0.0
1 : 1 : 0.0			100-140°	12	0.0	0.0
1 : 1 : 0.2		Pyridine	100-105°	4	49.4	61.4
1 : 1 : 0.2		"	95-98°	4	55.3	69.1
1 : 1 : 0.2		"	90°	4	61.2	80
1 : 1 : 0.2		"	80°	5	69.1	84
1 : 1 : 1		"	98-99°	6	41.5	
1 : 1 : 2		"	"	12	67.3	
1 : 1 : 3		"	"	"	69.1	
1 : 1 : 1		Piperidine	"	6	43.6	
1 : 1 : 6		Pyridine + traces of piperidine (Robin son's method)	117°	2.5 and then boiling	68.7	
1 : 1 : 10		Pyridine (Vorsatz)	Room	3 weeks	17	
1 : 1 :		" "	"	3 months.	17	
1 : 1		Ether, sufficient	"	3 weeks	0	

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